

Benzene fraction :

β -Setosterol-D-glucoside, m.p. 300° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -43^\circ$; tetraacetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 166-67°; acid hydrolysis furnished β -sitosterol (m.m.p. and co-tlc) and D-glucose (co-pc). The compound was shown to be identical with β -sitosterol-D-glucoside.

Acetone fraction :

It was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with different solvents and their mixture yielded two compounds: D(+)-Pinitol, m.p. 186°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic specimen, pentacetate, m.p. 98°; and meso-inositol, m.p. 218-219°, identical (ms and ir) with an authentic sample, hexaacetate, m.p. 215°.

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3-(p-Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide. A New Reagent for Gravimetric Determination of Nickel(II) and Palladium(II) and their Separation from Binary Mixture

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THE so-called hydroxytriazene has been recently shown from ir spectra to exist predominantly in the tautomeric N-oxide form¹. Such ligands have been used both as analytical reagents and as complex former²⁻⁷. We recommend in this communication a new triazene derivative, 3-(p-acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide for the gravimetric determination of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺. The reagent reacts with Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ quantitatively in the pH ranges, 6-10 and 1.5-10, forming deep yellow, Ni(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂ and buff coloured, Pd(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂ complexes, respectively. The determinations of both the metal ions in the presence of large number of foreign ions and from their binary mixture have been described.

Experimental

3-(p-Acetophenyl)-1-phenyltriazene-N-oxide : The reagent was prepared by coupling phenylhydroxylamine suspended in cooled acidified water with diazo salt of p-aminoacetophenone at 0°. The pH of the reaction mixture containing yellow pasty mass was raised around 5 by saturated sodium acetate solution and kept for 1 h. The light yellow compound was recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 158° (Found : N, 16.32; C, 65.60; H, 5.22. C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃ requires : N, 16.47; C, 65.88; H, 5.10%).

Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ solutions : MCl₂ (E. Merck, M= Ni or Pd) was dissolved in hydrochloric acid and the metal content was determined gravimetrically with dimethylglyoxime⁸.

A Cambridge bench model pH meter was used to record the acidity of the solutions. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

Procedure : Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (3.0-40 mg) were precipitated from hot solutions (200 ml) using at least 1.5 times the theoretical amounts of reagent in warm ethanol (15 ml) at the pH range 6-10 and 1.5-10 respectively, adjusted by dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The deep yellow Ni²⁺-complex and buff coloured Pd²⁺-complex were digested on boiling water-bath for 30 min and filtered hot through weighed Gooch crucibles no. 4 and 3, respectively, washed with hot water, dried at 110-20° and weighed as M(C₁₄H₁₃O₂N₃)₂. The gravimetric factors for nickel and palladium are 0.1036 and 0.1732, respectively.

The standard deviations for several determinations of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (9.0 mg each) were found to be ± 0.28 and $\pm 0.33\%$, respectively.

Separation and determination of Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ present in a binary mixture : Pd²⁺ was first determined from the binary mixture (150-200 ml) at pH 2.0 using reagent 3-4 times of the total metal ions in the usual way. The volume of the filtrate and the washing was then reduced to 200 ml and Ni²⁺ was determined following the procedure described.

Procedure in presence of diverse ions : Ni²⁺ and Pd²⁺ (9.0mg each) could be determined at pH 7.0 and 3.0, respectively in the presence of the following foreign ions using tartrate (1.0-1.5 g) as masking agent: Al³⁺, Bi³⁺, As³⁺, Ag⁺, Pb²⁺ and Sn²⁺, 30 mg each; Be²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻, VO₃⁻, ZrO²⁺, HfO²⁺, Nb^v, Ta^v, Rh³⁺, Pt²⁺, Cs²⁺ and TiO²⁺, 50 mg each. However Fe³⁺ (30 mg), Hg²⁺ and Cd²⁺ (50 mg each) and UO₃²⁺ (50 mg) needed ascorbic acid plus phosphoric acid, potassium iodide and ammonium acetate as the masking agents, respectively. Cr³⁺, Mn²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ donot interfere with the determination of Pd but do with Ni estimation. Anions, such as F⁻ (500 mg), SCN⁻ (100 mg), AsO₄²⁻ (100 mg), BO₃²⁻ (100 mg), oxalate and citrate (100 mg each) and PO₄²⁻ (200 mg) are tolerable in both the cases. Disodium

EDTA and CN^- interfere. Even trace amount of Au^{3+} interferes with Pd^{2+} estimation.

Results and Discussion

The precipitations of Ni^{2+} and Pd^{2+} complexes commence at pH 5.0 and 1.0 and are quantitative within the pH ranges 6-10 and 1.5-10, respectively. At least 1.5 times the theoretical amounts of the reagent are needed for complete precipitation of metal ions. Ethanolic solution of the reagent was found stable for several weeks. The complexes are insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents. Nickel and palladium complexes melt with decomposition at 253 and 285°, respectively. Analytical results indicate molecular formula, $\text{M}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3)_2$.

Infrared spectral bands of the reagent at 1 670, 3 205 and 1 290 cm^{-1} are due to $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{N}-\text{H}$ and $\text{N}-\text{O}$ stretching vibrations, respectively. In the spectrum of Ni^{2+} or Pd^{2+} complexes, the position of $\text{C}=\text{O}$ band remains unchanged while $\text{N}-\text{H}$ band disappears and a lowering in frequency of $\text{N}-\text{O}$ band is observed, suggesting the bonding through N of $\text{N}-\text{H}$ group after displacement of proton and through O of $\text{N}-\text{O}$ group.

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Use of some Visual Indicators for Direct Titrations with Dibromamine-T

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REDOX titrations in nonaqueous or partially aqueous media are, as a rule, followed potentiometrically. A search through the literature has revealed that the use of visual indicators for titrations in such media is very limited¹⁻⁷. As part of our investigations on novel redox titrants, we explore the possibility of using some visual indica-

tors for direct titrations with dibromamine-T, a typical oxidimetric titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium⁸⁻¹¹.

Experimental

Dibromamine-T (DBT) was prepared⁸ by bromination of chloramine-T (B.D.H.). A decinormal solution ($\sim 0.025 M$) of DBT was prepared by dissolving the dry sample (8.2 g) in anhydrous acetic acid (1 dm^3) and was standardised by the usual iodometric method and stored in an amber-coloured bottle. The six indicator solutions used for the titrations, viz., amaranth, indigo carmine, methyl orange, methyl red, *p*-ethoxychrysoidine and quinoline yellow were prepared by dissolving the dye stuffs in appropriate solvents by standard methods¹². Standard solutions ($\sim 0.1 N$, 500 ml) of potassium antimony tartarate (8.1 g), sodium sulphite (8.2 g), ascorbic acid (4.4 g), hydrazine sulphate (1.6 g), benzhydrazide (2.7 g), isoniazid (1.7 g), phenylhydrazinehydrochloride (1.8 g), semicarbazidehydrochloride (1.4 g), aniline (0.78 g), phenol (0.78 g) and anthranilic acid (1.1 g) were prepared by dissolving the specified amount of these substances in water. As^{3+} solution was prepared by dissolving As_2O_3 (2.5 g) in 1 *N* sodium hydroxide, neutralising it with 1 *N* sulphuric acid and making upto 500 ml with water. Standard solution (500 ml) of Fe^{2+} was prepared by dissolving 19.6 g of ferrous ammonium sulphate (19.6 g) in 2 *N* sulphuric acid and standard solution (500 ml) of 8-hydroxyquinoline (1.8 g) prepared in aqueous acetic acid (50%, v/v). The strengths of these reductant solutions were checked by standard methods^{12,14}.

The metal oxinates of Al^{3+} , Cd^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} were prepared by standard methods^{12,13}. To the solutions of the metal salts (2 *M*), an ethanolic solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline (6 *M* for Al^{3+} and 4 *M* for others) was added in small portions with stirring. The precipitated oxinates were filtered, washed with water and dried over P_4O_{10} . Metal anthranilates of Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} were prepared by mixing a solution of sodium anthranilate (4 *M*) and the respective metal salts (2 *M*) in neutral or weakly acidic medium. The metal anthranilates were filtered, washed with 0.2% solution of sodium anthranilate and finally with ethanol and dried over P_4O_{10} . Standard solutions of the metal oxinates and anthranilates were prepared by dissolving the required amounts in 500 ml of 2 *N* hydrochloric acid to give approximately 0.1 *N* solutions. The strengths of these solutions were checked by the bromate-bromide method^{12,14}.

The titrations were carried out at room temperature by the following method. To measured aliquots (10-20 ml) of the reductant solution taken in a flask, 2 *N* hydrochloric acid (5 ml) and other reagents such as potassium bromide (0.5 g), sodium acetate (0.5 g), etc., if required, were added. After